

Aluminium Chloride Catalysed Reaction of the Naphthols with Acrylic Esters A Direct Synthesis of Dihydronaphthacoumarins*

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Certain naturally occurring coumarins and coumarin derivatives possess anthelmintic properties¹⁻³. α - and β -Naphthacoumarins, their methyl derivatives as well as their reduced products are potent anthelmintic agents⁴. We have reported in a previous communication^{5,6} the reaction between phenols and methyl acrylate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride and dry hydrogen chloride for the synthesis of coumarin derivatives. Naphthols on condensation under similar conditions with methyl acrylate produce dihydronaphthacoumarins, which are converted to coumarins by dehydrogenation over Pd-C (10%). With methyl methacrylate, 3-methyl-naphthacoumarins are produced in a lesser yield.

α -Naphthol, on condensation with methyl acrylate in the presence of aluminium chloride and dry hydrogen chloride at 140-160°, furnished a mixture of 3:4-dihydro-7:8-benzocoumarin (Ia) m.p. 75° and β -(4-hydroxyl-1-naphthyl)-propionic acid (II), m.p.

*Part III of a series "Coumarin and Related Compounds".

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182-183°. The mixture was separated by chromatography over silica gel. Ia on dehydrogenation over Pd-C (10%) in diphenyl oxide⁷ gave 7:8-benzocoumarin (IIIa)⁸, m.p. 140-142° ($\lambda_{\max}$ 219, 265, 275, 308, 322 m μ ; $\log \epsilon = 4.6, 4.5, 4.6, 3.9, 4.0$) undepressed with an authentic sample⁹. Similarly with methyl methacrylate, 3-methyl-3:4-dihydro-7:8-benzocoumarin (Ib), m.p. 89-90°, was formed which on dehydrogenation gave 3-methyl-7:8-benzocoumarin (IIIb), m.p. 133°. ($\lambda_{\max}$ 222, 267, 277, 310, 323 m μ ; $\log \epsilon = 4.5, 4.5, 4.6, 3.9, 4.0$). With β -naphthol and methyl acrylate, 3:4-dihydro-5:6-benzocoumarin (IVa), m.p. 55° was produced. IVa on dehydrogenation gave 5:6-benzocoumarin (Va)¹⁰, m.p. 117-118° ($\lambda_{\max}$ 231, 250, 317 m μ ; $\log \epsilon = 4.8, 4.1, 4.0$) undepressed with an authentic sample.

With β -naphthol and methyl methacrylate, 3-methyl-3:4-dihydro-5:6-benzocoumarin (IVb), m.p. 105-106°, was formed. Dehydrogenation of IVb with Pd-C, gave 3-methyl-5:6-benzocoumarin (Vb)¹¹, m.p. 157-158° ($\lambda_{\max}$ 232.5, 317, 345 m μ ; $\log \epsilon = 4.7, 4.0, 4.1$). Construction of naphthacoumarins with hydroxyl group in the aromatic nucleus is presently under investigation**.

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**Satisfactory element analyses were obtained for all the compounds reported and homogeneity checked by T. L. C. U. V. spectra were determined in ethanol solution.